

Statistical Analysis of Marks Obtained At the first Year B.Ed. Semester One Examination

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Abstract :

This present paper reports the analytical study undertaken the relationship between Childhood & Growing up, Contemporary India & Education, Understanding Discipline & Subjects, Reading & Reflecting on Texts and practicum contains Diagnostic and Enriching the Teaching Skills, Lesson Planning Workshop & Demonstration lesson, Simulated Teaching Workshop, Teaching Aids Workshop, School Engagement and visit to innovative centers of pedagogy and leaning, Internal Examination (Semester Ist Assignment Internal Viva + Semester Ist External Examination), Language across school curriculum marks of teacher students. The practical marks is related to teacher educators attendance and punctuality, teacher educators attitude and methodology in teaching, teaching-learning process, teacher students performance and student teacher feedback, student educator and students teacher evaluation. There obtains a very close correlation between a conclusion that might somewhat modify these who are septic about giving weight age to internal assessment as lacking reliability. The total 50 B.Ed. First Year student teachers of this college were selected by stratified random sampling. Obtain marks out of 300 in university examination were taken as external and obtain marks out of 300 in college examination as internal evaluation. Findings were derived on the base of objectives, hypothesis, statistical analysis.

Key words:

Two year B. Ed, course, Assessment, Evaluation, Examination, Teacher students, feedback internal marks, and Theory examination marks, weight age of practical marks.

Introduction:

The training institution is concerned with the development of trainee teacher in all round development of his physical, social and emotional, teaching knowledge, skills, and personality qualities. As per NCTE norms, instead of the earlier one-year programme, the B.Ed. programme is two years' duration now, which can be completed in a maximum of three years from the date of admission to the programme. During the process of the teacher training of the teacher students has to be continually appraised with regard to the level of his intelligence, attainment, aptitude and interest and the method of teaching-learning, various skills to be adopted. The institution will work for a minimum of 36 hours in a week (five or six days), during which physical presence in the institution of all the teachers and students is necessary to ensure their availability for advice, guidance, dialogue and consultation as and when needed. The minimum attendance for students will be 80% for all course work and practical and 90% for school internship. The B.Ed. curriculum designed to integrate the study of subject knowledge, human development, pedagogical knowledge and communication skills. The programme will comprise three broad curricular areas: perspectives in education, curriculum and pedagogic studies, and engagement with the field. The courses under each of these curricular areas will be based on a close reading of original writings, seminar/term paper presentations and continuous engagement with the field. The subject offer Childhood & Growing up, Contemporary India & Education, Understanding Discipline & Subjects, Reading & Reflecting on Texts and practicum contains Diagnostic and Enriching the Teaching Skills, Lesson Planning Workshop & Demonstration lesson, Simulated Teaching Workshop, Teaching Aids Workshop, School Engagement and visit to innovative centers of pedagogy and leaning, Internal Examination (Semester Ist Assignment Internal Viva + Semester Ist External Examination), Language across school curriculum marks of teacher students. The traditional system of examinations which primarily measures the academic achievements. Several research studies are being made to bring to light the drawbacks of this system so that remedial steps can be taken.

The weight age given to the internal marks in the final evaluation of a student teacher achievement and performance in one such step. In examination and measurement the emphasis is upon includes all the changes that take place in the development of a balanced personality and measure the qualities of teacher students. The researcher to investigate the relationship between the final theory examination and internal marks in various practical's. The scheme of examination in the B. Ed. First year first semester course is as under

First Year

Semester –I								
Course	B.Ed. Courses	Hours		Credit	Exam Hours	Marks		
		Inst. Hrs	Learning Hrs			(sessional)	External (Theory)	Total
	Perspectives In Education - Theory							
1	Childhood & Growing up	60	00	04	3	30	70	100
2	Contemporary India & Education	60	00	04	3	30	70	100
	Curriculum & Pedagogical Studies							
3	Understanding Discipline & Subjects	30	00	02	02	15	35	50
	Enhancement in Professional Capacities(EPC)							
EPC -1	Reading & Reflecting on Texts	15	30	02	00	50	00	50
	Practicum							
A-1	Diagnostic and Enriching the Teaching Skills	60	00	02	--	50	00	50
A-2	Lesson Planning Workshop & Demonstration lesson	36	09	01	--	25	0	25
A-3	Simulated Teaching Workshop	30	12	01	--	25	0	25
A-4	Teaching Aids Workshop	24	12	01	--	25	0	25
A-5	School Engagement and visit to innovative centres of pedagogy and leaning	108	00	04	--	100	0	100
A-6	Internal Examination (Semester Ist Assignment Internal Viva + Semester Ist External Examination)							

A-6.1	Semester Ist Internal Assignment	12	10	02	--	10	0	10
A-6.2	Semester Ist Internal Viva	12	20		--	30	0	30
A-6.3	Semester Ist End Internal Examination	24	30		--	10	0	10
A-7	Language across school curriculum	15	15	01	--	25	0	25
Total		486	+138	24	08	425	175	600

The teaching profession requiring through knowledge as well as practical skills. Teacher students work with the physical body. The training is totally related to practical work. Practical work develop the teacher students work with the complex of the human mind and personality. The practical work is based on long established learning theory such as feedback, guidance, demo, reinforcement, were adopted.

Objectives:

- 1.To compare the internal and theory examination marks of student teacher.
- 2.To study the student teacher attitude towards practical and theory examination.
- 3.To study the Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. first year student teachers.
2. To know the correlation between Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. first year Student teachers.
3. To study the Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. first year student teachers in context of their faculty.
4. To know the correlation between Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. first year students teachers in context of their faculty.

Research Sample-

For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of the sample consisted statistical Analysis of Marks Obtained at The B.Ed.first year first semester Examination (2015) of S.M.T. Government College of Education, Kolhapur.

Analysis under different aspects:

The achievement of teacher

SR. No.	Seat No.	Course 1		Course 2		Course 3		EPC	Pract	Total	%
1	579	34	21	32	25	17	11	30	229	399	66.5
2	580	41	23	31	26	25	12	32	238	428	71.3
3	581	39	23	39	26	24	13	31	242	437	72.8
4	582	41	20	40	25	22	12	34	231	425	70.8
5	583	37	23	38	25	27	13	32	236	431	71.8
6	584	42	22	36	26	27	13	35	233	434	72.3
7	585	43	23	40	27	21	12	34	235	435	72.5
8	586	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	587	49	27	44	28	27	13	36	262	486	81
10	588	50	25	43	28	25	12	31	249	463	77.2
11	589	40	25	34	27	18	12	31	235	422	70.3
12	590	45	25	41	25	27	11	33	239	446	74.3
13	591	42	24	39	26	26	12	33	243	445	74.2
14	592	36	24	37	27	23	11	35	237	430	71.7

15	593	44	23	37	28	26	22	25	236	441	73.5
16	594	50	24	46	28	27	11	32	253	471	78.5
17	595	50	23	53	26	26	12	32	235	457	76.2
18	596	47	26	50	28	27	11	34	250	473	78.8
19	597	38	19	41	24	20	12	34	235	423	70.5
20	598	48	23	52	28	23	10	34	259	477	79.5
21	599	47	25	50	29	23	11	34	255	474	79
22	600	38	19	15	27	18	12	32	239	400	66.7
23	601	51	22	55	28	26	12	32	246	472	78.7
24	602	44	23	48	26	17	11	34	248	451	75.2
25	603	44	27	44	27	26	11	33	245	457	76.2
26	604	41	23	39	27	23	11	35	237	436	72.7
27	605	50	25	45	26	21	12	31	244	454	75.7
28	606	42	23	43	27	25	11	33	240	444	74
29	607	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	608	39	24	43	26	19	11	32	245	439	73.2
31	609	33	23	39	26	21	12	36	236	426	71
32	610	51	23	46	28	25	13	32	252	470	78.3
33	611	41	25	48	27	20	11	35	246	453	75.5
34	612	48	25	57	27	26	12	33	242	470	78.3
35	613	37	23	30	25	20	9	25	231	400	66.7
36	614	47	26	33	26	24	12	34	251	453	75.5
37	615	41	23	40	27	26	11	34	239	441	73.5
38	616	43	24	44	26	24	11	32	230	434	72.3
39	617	36	23	41	27	23	11	35	240	436	72.7
40	618	45	26	37	28	25	11	33	250	455	75.8
41	619	34	24	32	27	19	12	33	248	429	71.5
42	620	51	24	39	26	25	12	33	247	457	76.2
43	621	43	23	42	26	23	12	35	235	439	73.2
44	622	42	26	46	27	25	11	30	250	457	76.2
45	623	37	22	40	26	24	12	35	232	428	71.3
46	624	43	25	55	28	27	11	33	252	474	79
47	625	42	24	42	26	24	12	32	247	449	74.8
48	626	41	24	46	27	23	12	33	242	448	74.7
49	627	36	22	43	26	23	11	35	220	416	69.3
50	628	19	25	0	27	26	12	31	250	390	65

The result of theory examination and practical marks of each teacher-students were then calculated and statistical analysis was done for further analysis were defined. The mean of percentage of marks is 70.90.

Graph -1 Shows the Course wise mark obtained by the student teacher.

Graph -2 Shows the mark obtained in EPC and Practical by the student teacher

Graph -3 Shows the Percentage of marks obtained by the student teacher.

Conclusion –

The teacher-students come into the profession and as existing teachers learn more and develop new ideas. The teacher training is of a highly complex which requires considerable knowledge a wide variety of skills and positive attitudes. The interesting point here is that teacher educators who carry out curriculum planning in a teacher-students group frequently derive from experience of personal relationship and the practical work in groups.

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